

Airway_Smooth_Muscle time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 1606

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 972

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 827

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 1305

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 513

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 1527

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 539

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 842

Basal_cell time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 1424

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 1019

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 1187

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 1120

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 972

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 1098

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 1201

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 1123

Bud_tip_adjacent time clusters

Bud_tip_progenitor time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 1563

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 1340

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 1286

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 1418

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 688

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 1478

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 699

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 1119

Cartilage time clusters

Club-like_secretory time clusters

Endothelial time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 941

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 1690

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 954

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 1089

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 1271

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 1256

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 1302

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 1403

Epithelial time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 1085

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 1154

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 1116

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 1167

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 1547

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 981

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 1486

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 1006

Goblet-like_secretory time clusters

Hematopoietic, B_Cells time clusters

Hematopoietic, Macrophage time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 901

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 1203

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 865

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 1130

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 1103

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 842

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 1090

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 1658

Hematopoietic,_Natural_Killer_Cell time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 1050

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 839

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 910

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 998

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 999

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 1352

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 1031

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 976

Hematopoietic, T_Cells time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 777

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 882

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 795

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 670

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 934

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 1251

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 1064

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 1310

Immune time clusters

Mesenchyme_RSPO2+ time clusters

Mesenchyme_SERPINF1-high time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 1174

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 832

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 866

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 1137

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 548

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 1407

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 609

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 1208

Multiciliated_cell time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 1525

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 732

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 1615

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 1903

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 1298

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 553

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 1092

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 814

Multiciliated_precursor time clusters

Neuroendocrine time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 1496

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 1290

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 1242

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 1149

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 1086

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 921

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 1019

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 1188

Pericyte time clusters

RBC time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 988

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 1407

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 1237

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 928

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 1059

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 1350

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 1337

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 1160

Secretory_progenitor time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 414

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 1704

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 1512

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 1113

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 649

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 1448

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 1476

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 872

Submucosal_gland_basal time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 1406

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 1414

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 1448

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 980

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 1268

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 1490

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 1138

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 1428

Submucosal_gland time clusters

